

Aleksandra Krkoleva Mateska
Vesna Borozan
Petar Krstevski
Rubin Taleski
University Ss. Cyril and Methodius in Skopje, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technologies
Stefan Borozan
Imperial College London, Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering

GAP ANALYSES BETWEEN THE LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK OF THE ELECTRICITY SECTOR IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA AND THE EUROPEAN LEGISLATION

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a critical analysis of the current development of the electricity sector legislation in the Republic of North Macedonia in comparison with the corresponding European Union (EU) legal framework.

Namely, the introductory review instantly locates the strategic interest of North Macedonia within the political sphere of the EU and the need for a consistent harmonization of the national law. Furthermore, it is evident that the path to full EU harmonization in the electricity sector goes across cooperation and fulfilment of the obligations undertaken with the Energy Community (EnC) Treaty. This Treaty is especially important for North Macedonia because it is the first legally binding agreement that the country has signed with the EU. Therefore, tracking the regular accomplishments of the requirements relating to the Treaty, as well as the attitude of the competent institutions and of the professional and broader public in North Macedonia toward it, reflects a picture of the overall readiness and seriousness of the reform process towards EU accession.

Finally, considering the dynamics of EU energy law development, especially in the current turbulent state of energy crises, the EnC Contracting Parties are always lagging behind in its transposition and implementation. This paper identifies the immediate pending obligations of North Macedonia in that process.

Keywords: electricity legal framework, national law harmonization, gap analysis

1 INTRODUCTION

Reforms in the energy sector which are instituted through the application of the EnC legislation are not only a precondition for further harmonization with the EU Law, but also represent a comprehensive process which is expected to help the development of a cost-effective and sustainable energy system. In fact, this process is an important segment of the preparations of the Republic of North Macedonia for the accession process to the EU and in general, for the overall economic growth of the country.

This paper consists of two parts, the former being a short review of the EU and EnC Law related to electricity markets. The review is used to perform gap analysis of the national against the EnC target legislation, which is contained in the latter part of the paper. The gap analysis is based on extensive investigations of legislation in the electricity sector of the Republic of North Macedonia, presented in earlier publications of the authors [1] and [2]. The goal of this paper is to provide a brief overview of

the current situation including update to the state presented in [1] and [2], as well as to draw a comparison of the accomplishments against the EnC and EU objectives. The overview of the state of affairs and of the objectives shall provide the groundwork for further monitoring of legislative changes in the pertinent areas, but also an overview of the country's progress towards fulfilment of objectives laid down in the EnC Treaty.

2 ELECTRICITY MARKET LEGISLATION AT EUROPEAN LEVEL

2.1 European Union Electricity Legal Framework

Until recently, the EU electricity sector was governed by the Third Legislative Package for Electricity and Gas Markets (Third Package), which fell short in defining and facilitating the use of advanced flexible technologies and a large number of new power system and power market operation concepts. Since then, there have been developments in legislation, mainly with the adoption of the Clean Energy for all Europeans Package (CEP), that remove certain barriers for advanced technologies and acknowledge several novel concepts related to electricity markets and power system security, operation, and control. Nevertheless, the process of legislative reforms is not complete, and there are several important pieces of regulation that ought to be prepared and adopted to allow for full implementation of the concepts promoted with the CEP.

2.1.1 Clean Energy for All Europeans Package

CEP was adopted in 2019 and its primary goal is to aid the decarbonization of EU's energy system in line with the ambitious mandatory climate targets by 2030. These targets are stipulated within the new Governance Regulation of the Energy Union and Climate Action (Governance Regulation) [3] that is a part of CEP.

In addition to the Governance Regulation, legal acts that comprise CEP can be conditionally classified in two groups based on their dominant contribution to the priority measures:

- Climate targets of the Energy Union (energy efficiency and renewable energy)
 - Directive (EU) 2018/844 on the energy performance of buildings,
 - Directive (EU) 2018/2001 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (recast) (RED II), and
 - Directive (EU) 2018/2002 on energy efficiency.
- Electricity market and security of supply
 - Directive (EU) 2019/944 on common rules for the internal market for electricity (recast) (IEM-Directive),
 - Regulation (EU) 2019/943 on the internal electricity market (recast) (IEM-Regulation),
 - Regulation (EU) 2019/941 on risk-preparedness in the electricity sector (Risk Regulation), and
 - Regulation (EU) 2019/942 on the establishment of the Agency for Cooperation of Energy Regulators (ACER) (recast).

In the following subsections a short description of the novelties introduced by the legal acts that create the electricity market legislation is given.

2.1.1.1 Renewables Directive

The RED II [26] for the first time introduces the following three concepts: i) renewables self-consumption, laying down the legal foundations for end users or customers to produce electricity from Renewable Energy Sources (RES) for own needs, but also to store and sell surplus electricity, ii) renewable energy cooperatives, and iii) new or reformulated criteria on sustainability and Green House Gases emissions savings of individual biofuels, bio-liquids or biomass fuels.

The RED II establishes a new binding target for the EU of 32% RES in energy consumption by 2030, including a review clause by 2023 for an upward revision of the EU level target. The implementation of this directive should improve the design and stability of RES Support Schemes, it should deliver real streamlining and reduction of administrative procedures and should establish a clear and stable regulatory self-consumption framework for RES. Furthermore, RED II increases the level of ambitions for application of RES in transportation and heating/cooling sectors. RED II also promotes cooperation among EU Member States (MSs) and with countries outside the EU, for mutual assistance in the achievement of target percentage for RES. Cooperation mechanisms can be in the form of: statistical renewable energy transfers, joint projects for RES, and joint Support Schemes for RES.

The adoption of the Fit for 55 package requested substantial changes to existing EU energy legislation to include a much higher share of RES in the energy mix of the EU and its MSs. It also required a revision of RED II. Following this, in July 2021, along with the adoption of Fit for 55, the European Commission (EC) proposed a revised RED II [4]. The EC's proposal for the revised RED II is supposed to double the share of RES in the energy mix until 2030 by increasing the binding EU minimum RES share in final energy consumption by 40%. To achieve this, a comprehensive framework for RES deployment across all sectors of the economy is to be set in motion and supported by sector-specific targets at EU and national level.

Some notable provisions in the revised RED II aim at creating a credit mechanism to incentivise renewable energy consumption in transport, facilitating collective Power Purchase Agreements for RES generators, introducing a new EU-wide labelling methodology for industrial products manufactured using renewable energy, and establishing a pilot project to foster cross-border cooperation on renewables. The sustainability of biofuels has also been addressed, for instance through the creation of Support Schemes that align with the biomass cascading principle.

During the Parliamentary procedure for adoption of a revised RED II, in July 2022, the Parliamentary Committee on Industry, Research and Energy reported a need for further accommodation of the legislative proposal for the purpose of incorporating the goals and targets of REPowerEU plan. There are several promising takeaways from this report. Notably, MSs are encouraged to aim for 5% newly installed capacities of both storage technologies and innovative RES technologies and are required to develop at least two cross-border RES projects before 2026. Trilogue negotiations between the Parliament, the Council and the EC are still ongoing¹.

2.1.1.2 Electricity Directive and Electricity Regulation

The IEM-Directive [5] and IEM-Regulation [6] aim to introduce a new energy market design. This part of CEP is targeted towards adjusting the EU internal electricity market model to cope with the challenges of the energy transition, i.e., to make the market better connected (integrated) and better protected from blackouts of the power system. In addition, this part of CEP should support the integration of electricity from renewables, as well as to be better adjusted to the needs of all customers.

These acts introduce for the first time a definition of energy storage systems, as a crucial resource in power systems to allow for more flexibility to accommodate an increasing share of renewable energy in the grid. Another novelty is the recognition of new market entities of citizen energy communities as a category of cooperation of citizens or local actors in the field of energy. The new market model aims to provide incentives for consumers to become more active and to contribute to keeping the electricity system stable by trading their consumption flexibility, which includes smart charging of electric vehicles and self-generated electricity. Furthermore, these acts profoundly address the issues of customer protection, supply switching, and energy poverty.

The IEM-Regulation also introduces cyber security care as part of the tasks of ACER, the European Network of Transmission System Operators (ENTSO-E) and of the Association for the European Distribution System Operators (EU DSO Entity) and it imposes an establishment of a new Network Code on Cyber Security.

¹ 20 January 2023

2.1.1.3 Risk Regulation

Secure operation of power systems and functioning electricity markets are prerequisites for secure and continuous supply of electricity. But even when these conditions are expected to be met, there are factors that may influence or disrupt supply of electricity. These factors may be both natural and man-made. Their effects can be easily spread to neighbouring systems as power systems are interconnected infrastructures. The consequences of disruptions in supply may have regional impacts in economy, environment and social interactions.

The Risk Regulation [7] is a legal act from the CEP which focuses on the issue of secure supply of electricity. It sets a framework for cooperation among EU MSs in preventing, preparing for and managing large scale electricity crisis, as well as for monitoring the security of electricity supply in the EU. This Regulation also considers the possible cooperation between EU MSs and EnC Contracting Parties in the area of secure electricity supply, which may include identification of electricity crisis scenarios, defining electricity crisis and establishment of risk-preparedness plans.

2.1.2 Network Codes

The electricity sectors in EU MSs are further governed by a set of regulations that are known as Network Codes (NCs). The existing Electricity NCs were adopted in the period 2015 – 2017 with the aim to unify power system operation and market rules across the EU for the purpose of creating a functional Internal Market for Electricity. This set of regulations formally belongs to the Third Package and comprises the following acts:

- Connection Codes
 - High Voltage Direct Current Connections,
 - Demand Connection Code (DCC), and
 - Requirements for Generators (RfG).
- Market Codes
 - Capacity Allocation & Congestion Management (CACM),
 - Forward Capacity Allocation (FCA), and
 - Electricity Balancing (EBGL).
- Operation Codes
 - System Operations (SOGL), and
 - Emergency and Restoration (ER).

The process of preparation of amendments to these NCs and their subsequent adoption to comply with the legislation introduced by CEP is ongoing within EU institutions.

2.1.2.1 Forward Capacity Allocation

FCA [8] prescribes rules for long term markets, which allow market players to hedge future price risk for periods defined in the forward contract (weeks, months, quarters or years). For this purpose, and to enhance cross-border exchange of electricity, this Regulation prescribes rules for forward allocation of physical and financial transmission rights. However, novel provisions in CEP dictate the fact that the creation of a new EU Electricity Market Model is necessary. Revisions of the forward market are argued in ACER's recent Policy Paper on the Further Development of the EU Electricity Forward Market [9].

2.1.2.2 Capacity Allocation and Congestion Management

CACM [10] is the basis of the European single market for electricity. It sets methodologies for calculation and allocation of transmission capacities in different market timeframes, defines regions for calculation of capacities and zones for bid submissions, as well as rules for operation of day-ahead and intraday electricity markets. CACM stands strictly for implicit coordinated capacity auctions. It also sets out to harmonise cross-border markets operation in Europe to increase competitiveness and renewables'

integration. The implementation of CACM presents impressive results in advancing the EU Day-ahead and intraday electricity markets [11].

2.1.2.3 Electricity Balancing

EBGL [12] promotes integration, coordination and harmonization of electricity balancing rules in order to facilitate the efficient use of available balancing resources as well as to allow new players such as demand response and renewables to take part in this market. This should help to increase security of supply, limit emissions and diminish costs to customers.

Namely, the objective of EBGL is to foster balancing market integration with the aim of reducing total costs and to increase social welfare while ensuring operational security. EBGL provides a definition of the concept of “Balancing energy”, which is provided by Balance Service Providers (BSPs). This energy is needed so that the Transmission System Operators (TSOs) balance the deviations between supply and demand in real-time. The BSPs should meet the necessary technical requirements to be able to deliver this service. Balancing can be provided by a wide range of technologies including small-scale, renewable, and conventional generation, energy storage and demand response. Therefore, the EBGL provides opportunities for all potential sources of balancing, fostering competition and thus maximizing social welfare gain. The EBGL are guided by the notion that actions which are not explicitly forbidden, like participation or initiative for cooperation, are allowed.

Balancing market design and arrangements cannot be fully decoupled from real time system operation as they occur in real time, and consequently, SOGL [13] is also relevant for the discussion of electricity balancing. The SOGL primarily addresses three aspects of balancing: the harmonisation of reserve categories, the activation strategy for balancing energy in real-time and the sizing of reserves.

2.1.2.4 System Operation

SOGL [13] specifies TSO activities to manage secure operation of their electricity grid, considering the integration of renewables and flexibility resources, as well as increased interconnections and cross-border competition. It also makes regional coordination a legal obligation for grid operators.

In addition, SOGL regulates the coordination and data exchange between TSOs, between TSOs and Distribution System Operators (DSOs), as well as between TSOs or DSOs and Significant Grid Users (SGUs) in planning and in close to real-time operations.² This includes rules and responsibilities for the approval of Key Organisation Requirements, Roles and Responsibilities (KORRR) relating to Data Exchange [14], the implementation of specific aspects of the data exchange, and the agreements on processes and format for data exchanges between key players.

2.1.2.5 Emergency and Restoration

ER [15] prescribes the steps and processes that TSOs have to follow in case of incidents in their grid. These processes involve the highest standards and practices in dealing with emergency, blackout, and restoration states, with the main objective to bring the system back to normal state of operation.

ER provides harmonized requirements for the establishment of the System Defence Plan and Restoration Plan by TSOs, thus ensuring the overall efficiency of these plans at the European level. In addition, it endeavours to ensure the continuity of energy transactions during Emergency, Blackout or Restoration State and provides the conditions under which such transactions could be suspended [15].

2.1.2.6 Connection Codes

RfG [16] harmonizes standards that generators must respect to connect to the grid in order to boost the market participation of generation technology and increase competitiveness.

DCC [17] lays down the requirements for grid connection of: i) transmission-connected demand facilities; ii) transmission-connected distribution facilities; iii) distribution systems, including closed distribution systems; iv) demand units, used by a demand facility or a closed distribution system to

² Article 40 of SOGL

provide demand response services to relevant system operators and relevant TSOs. DCC also lays down the obligations to ensure that system operators make appropriate use of the demand facilities' and distribution systems' capabilities in a transparent and non-discriminatory manner.

2.2 Legal Framework of the Energy Community

In general, the implementation level of the EU energy and environmental law in the Energy Community Contracting Parties is limited to the basic documents of the EU Third Package for Electricity and Gas Markets.

The first step towards alignment with the current EU law in the related areas was done at the 19th EnC Ministerial Council of 30 November 2021³, when the first set of CEP documents and commitments was adopted in the EnC Law. This set covers legislation in the areas of governance, energy efficiency, renewables, electricity market design, and security of supply rules, which should enter into force as follows:

- Governance Regulation, with a general transposition deadline until 31 December 2024,
- RED II, with a general transposition deadline until 31 December 2022,
- Directive (EU) 2018/2002 on energy efficiency, with a general transposition deadline until 31 December 2025.

The alignment with the current EU law continued with the Decision of the 20th EnC Ministerial Council of 15 December 2022⁶ and the adopting the following CEP documents:

- IEM-Directive, with a general transposition deadline until 31 December 2023,
- IEM-Regulation, with a general transposition deadline until 31 December 2024,
- Risk Regulation, with a general transposition deadline until 31 December 2024, and
- Regulation (EU) 2019/942 on the establishment of the ACER (recast), with a general transposition deadline until 31 December 2024.

However, the most important development to paving the way for establishing the SEE Electricity Market happened at the 20th EnC Ministerial Council⁷ by adoption, based on the previous long-lasting negotiation and adaptation process with the EC, of the Market and System Operation NCs deriving from the Third Package for Electricity and Gas Markets. The adoption of the Market and System Operation NCs has become a reality after incorporating a new reciprocity mechanism within the EnC Treaty, which makes possible market couplings between EU MSs and EnC Contracting Parties. The final set of NCs to be incorporated in the EnC law included the following:

- FCA, with a general implementation deadline until 1 January 2024,
- CACM, with a general implementation deadline until 1 January 2024,
- EBGL, with a general implementation deadline until 1 January 2024,
- SOGL, with a general implementation deadline until 1 January 2024, and
- ER, with a general implementation deadline until 1 January 2024.

³ <https://www.energy-community.org/legal/decisions.html>

⁴ Renewables, energy efficiency and greenhouse gas reduction targets for 2030 were adopted at the next Ministerial Council in December 2022, following the finalization of a study by the European Commission

⁵ Each Contracting Party shall bring into force the laws, regulations, and administrative provisions necessary to comply with points 5 to 10 of the Article 1, and points 3 and 4 of paragraph 2 of the Annex to Directive (EU) 2018/2002 by 30 June 2023.

⁶ <https://www.energy-community.org/legal/decisions.html>

⁷ <https://www.energy-community.org/legal/decisions.html>

3 IMPLEMENTATION OF ELECTRICITY MARKET LEGISLATION IN NORTH MACEDONIA

The detailed information in [1] and [2] clearly indicates that the Energy Law [18] is the basis for implementing the robust reform process for transposition of the EU Law in the North Macedonia’s electricity sector. The implementation of this Law and the relevant secondary legislation adopted by competent state institutions puts the country among the EnC Contracting Parties which have transposed the Third Package in their national legislation. Further in this chapter, an overview is presented of the most relevant bylaws and other documents which further define the legislative will in the areas of direct relevance for this paper – the electricity market. As an update to the situation presented in [1] and [2], it specifically makes reference to the main achievements in the past three to four years, implemented with a view to further harmonise the provisions of the latest Energy Law [18] and to prepare for full implementation of the NCs which are outlined in the subchapter 2.1.2. In addition, preparations for drafting a new Energy Law of North Macedonia, which shall transpose the requested CEP documents from the EnC Law, have started during the first half of 2023. As presented in the subchapter 2.2, the implementation deadlines for all these legal acts are in the near future.

Figure 1 presents part of the legislative acts adopted or approved by relevant institutions, which enable the most significant reform achievements related to the implementation of European legislation.

Figure 1 Overview of the key achievements from the implementation of EnC legislation

One of the key requirements introduced by the Third Package was met with the implementation of the Energy Law and the finalization of the ownership unbundling of the TSO - MEPSO. Moreover, the certification process of MEPSO as a TSO was completed successfully. The extended competences of the ERC and the implementation of the Third Package has enabled ERC to apply for membership in the working bodies of ACER and thus to contribute to the further advancement of the work of ERC. Now, ERC has a status of observer in the ACER’s Electricity Working Group. An important contribution to achieving this status was the complete implementation of the EU REMIT Regulation [19] after adequately amending Energy Law [18] and adopting the new Rulebook on Market Monitoring [20]. By the last amendments to the Energy Law [18], the EU TEN-E Regulation [21] was transposed to the

national legislation, thus achieving one more milestone on the way to EU harmonization. All these achievements are acknowledged by the last EnC Secretariat Annual Implementation Report 2022, [22].

Figure 1 presents yet another essential step which contributes to the process of implementation of Market NCs, which is the establishment of a National Operator of the Organised Electricity Market in North Macedonia – MEMO. This is considered as an exceptional achievement among EnC Contracting Parties. Even more important is that in September 2020, by Government decision, MEMO was designated as the Nominated Electricity Market Operator (NEMO), in line with the Market NCs of the EU, which made our country the first of the EnC Contracting Parties to have implemented such a decision⁸. Until that time, MEMO undertook series of activities for the establishment of the first organized electricity market (the Day-ahead and Intraday market) in North Macedonia, and for its coupling with neighbouring markets into a single electricity market of the EU⁹. On a session held on 6 April 2023 the ERC adopted a Decision to approve the Rules for Operation of the organized electricity market and MEMO's Day-ahead auctions went live on 10 May 2023¹⁰, which is an important step towards achieving the European Electricity Market Target Model and further market coupling with neighbouring markets.

According to the assessment of the level of the application of EnC legislation in North Macedonia [22] the estimate is that all the actions taken for implementation of the Energy Law [3] and the development and adoption of secondary legislation, above all through the expertise of the ERC, has led to the establishment of “advanced model of electricity market with high level of openness”.

In relation the implementation of the NCs, the Energy Law prescribes their direct applicability, however, [22] states that no NC has been translated and published officially as a legislative act. The transmission grid code was amended accordingly in December 2021 to implement the NCs. The distribution grid was amended in 2022, but it needs further changes to reflect all required parameters of the Connection Codes [22].

Upon adoption of the Energy Law and of series of bylaws described in detail in [**Error! Reference source not found.**], the wholesale and retail electricity market were completely transformed. Figure 2 presents a general picture of the achievements made.

⁸ “North Macedonia becomes first Contracting Party to designate market operator in line with EU CACM”, <https://www.energy-community.org/news/Energy-Community-News/2020/09/14.html>

⁹ MEPSO, that is MEMO, has signed Memorandum of Understanding on market coupling with Bulgaria, and Albania, and in 2020 it was also negotiating with Greece, <http://memo.mk/Public/Post.aspx?id=32fafd22-eba3-4fc4-be0b-1223e7f41500>

¹⁰ https://dam.memo.mk/?page_id=30312

Figure 2 Achievements and processes in relation to electricity market liberalization processes

Table 1 presents a summary of achievements made in the area of electricity markets and in the area of security of supply, which is closely connected to the integration of electricity markets.

Table 1: Achievements in the areas of electricity markets and security of supply - summary

Area	Process /adopted acts	Status
Electricity market	TSO is unbundled and certified	
	DSO is legally and functionally unbundled	
	MEMO is established	
	MEMO is designated as NEMO	
	ERC is established and is independent	
	Organised market (day ahead) is functional, intraday not established yet	
	Electricity market rules are adopted	
	Balancing market is functional (balancing reserves and capacity are procured through a platform managed by MEPSO)	
	Wholesale market is fully liberalised	
	Energy Law amended to transpose CACM & direct transposition of NCs is enabled, thus the framework for market coupling is set.	
	Transmission grid code amended to transpose NCs, distribution grid code requires amendments.	
	Retail market is liberalised	
	Universal supplier is elected through competitive bidding procedure	
	Supplier of last resort is elected through competitive bidding procedure	
	Security of supply	Energy Law amended and Rulebook on Market Monitoring adopted to transpose REMIT
Energy Strategy adopted (2020)		
Annual program for protection of vulnerable energy customers adopted (2023)		
Planning energy balance adopted (2022)		
Law on Security of Network and Information Systems to transpose the NIS Directive		
Participation in the regional office for auction of transmission capacities		
Coupling of electricity market with neighbouring countries		
Unfulfilled requirements		Fulfilled

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper provides a comprehensive overview of the developments in the EU legislation following the implementation of the Third Package. The paper focuses on the latest package of energy related legislation, i.e., CEP, which focuses both on energy and climate, aiming to provide a wide framework that will foster the energy transition. The comprehensive overview clearly shows the developments in the EU and the actions taken by the EnC to align its legislation to these developments. Albeit the recognizable achievements of North Macedonia in implementation of the Third Package, it is

necessary to note that there are still actions that need to be taken, especially to fully implement the required NCs. As described in section 2.2, there are new tasks that need to be fulfilled to start the process of implementation of CEP. In fact, the investigation presented in this paper shows very plainly that the process of alignment with the EU law is not complete yet, since the challenges for EnC Contracting Parties are renewed with every new development of the EU Law and EnC Law, as it is shown in Chapter 2 of this paper.

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